

Developing Entrepreneurial Skills through Business Education Program to Curb Youth Restiveness for Sustainable National Development

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Abstract: The paper focus on entrepreneur skill through business education program to curb restiveness for sustainable development. Need for entrepreneur skills acquisition were identified, business education program and functions of entrepreneur were identified and sorted out as the types of entrepreneur in our present society. Conclusion was drawn which include effort towards creating good initiatives in order to develop our dear societies as it become the focus in 21st century. Therefore parents and business society should emulate a kind of economy strategies like China, Germany, and America etc. in order to provide means of surviving strategies among individuals in the entire nation.

Keywords: Developing, Entrepreneurial Skill, Business Education Program, Restiveness, Sustainable, Youth and National Development.

I. Introduction

Nations wealth or poverty depends on the capacity it quality skills and acquisitions acquired or not acquired in the development of the economy. Nations like America, China, Singer pore, Germany, Indonesia etc. used their well experience's to develop their nations with manipulation of skills through individuals and self-help to rise the economy to a level where others nations cannot compete with. The sharp decline for employment opportunities emerges the high desires for entrepreneurial education in our country, where hope of tomorrow is in a continuous increase in the society and the government is on the pressing needs of hard works through skills, initiative and good performance to curb social devices among youths. Indeed, business education programmes are structure through well curriculum planners that catered the desires of our national growth. At the same time, business education program provides students with information about all aspect of business. Business education program should include courses in accounting, marketing, fiancé and management.

Who is an entrepreneur in a sustainable development, looking at the conceptual definition of entrepreneur Usman (2006) identified that some who once assumes the financial risk of beginning and managing a new venture. The venture can be based on total new idea, new way of doing things, a new location, or attempting something on one else has done before. He is a person who detects a previously untapped opportunity to make substantial profit (either by lowering the cost of production existing goods/services, or by creating brands new ways for people to satisfy their wants through new products). Schumpeter (2012) identified entrepreneur as innovator or who implement changes within market structure through the carrying out of new combinations which can take different dimensions such as the introduction of new goods or quality, bringing of method of production, the opening of a new market, the congress of a new sources of supply of new materials or parts, the carrying out of the new organization of an industry.

Hisrich (2002) states that entrepreneur as a process of creating something different with values by deviating the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financing psychological and social risk, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and person satisfaction.

Entrepreneur is referred to an attempt to create value, through recognition of business opportunity, the management or risk-taking appropriate to the opportunity and through the communicative and management skills to mobilize human, financial and materials resources necessary to bring a project to function (Koa and Stevenson, 1984).

Usman (2006) states that entrepreneur is the process of identifying, developing and bringing a vision to life, the vision may be innovative idea, and opportunity, or simply a better way to do something. The end result of this process is the creation of new venture formed under conditions of risk and considerable uncertainty.

II. ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS

Many industry observers have debated on the origin of entrepreneurship. Fact to note here is that most scholars who debate the origin of entrepreneurship are either economists or historians. The common forum accepts that the concept of entrepreneur is derived from the French concept *entreprenidie*, which means closely with the English concept of business conduct (to undertake). From the business point of view, to undertake simply means to start a business.

The entrepreneurship theory has been changing throughout several decades of business growth and has received numerous definitions and characteristics from different scholars, who believe that some qualities are common among most entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurship foundations are based on economics and other discipline such as history, politics, education, culture, experience and networking. Schompeter (Joseph Alioj Schompeter), who was an Austrian born American Economist and political scientist) told that the coming together of various desperate theories forms a generalized set of entrepreneurship skills and guidelines. Schompeter, then listed the characteristics of entrepreneurs as:

1. Risk bearers
2. Coordinators and organized
3. Gap fillers
4. Leaders
5. Innovators
6. Creative imitator.

He concludes that although these features are not the only ones, but they do go a long way in explaining why some people become entrepreneurs while others do not.

What then is an entrepreneurship? Entrepreneurship is a system of operating business in which opportunities existing with the scope of market are exploited. Self employment necessitates that any available opportunities within the economic system should be utilized in the creation and erection of new organizations. A potential entrepreneur should show the interest to seek out investment opportunities in the market, so that they can run the enterprise successfully based on the identifiable opportunities. Thus, going through the above responsibilities of an entrepreneur, the term “entrepreneurship” has been finally defined as a function which covers multiple functions such as:

1. Building organizations.
2. Providing self employment.
3. Utilization of available resources.
4. Innovation applied to the novel concept.
5. Bringing together multiple factors of production in a tangible manner.
6. Identifying and exploiting business opportunities within the available market.

III. QUALITIES/TRAITS OF AN ENTREPRENEURS

Traits of an entrepreneur are as follows:

1. Time management.
2. Self motivation.
3. Financial know-how.
4. Vision and leadership skills.
5. Sales.
6. Conflict and consensus management skills.
7. Technical skills.
8. Communication skills.
9. Ethics and morals.
10. Inter-personal skills.
11. Problem solving skills.
12. Administration.
13. Self confidence.

IV. TYPES OF ENTREPRENEURS

Assessing the types of entrepreneur's skills in our present business programmes, Stoke (1995) classified the types of entrepreneur into three categories such as:

- i. **Craft-man Entrepreneurs:** These are a person who poses the skills techniques and expertise to provide the service or product directly to the market. These are classified as small business owners and self employed persons. They usually have the technical know-how and skills as a result of training in vocational and technical skills. These types of entrepreneurs are found in business like joinery, carpentry, hair dressing, tailoring, welding, mechanical works etc.
- ii. **Promoter:** This is the type of entrepreneur who establishes, grow develops and sells different business or business idea in the pursuit of gains. He usually initiates an idea, develops it and later relinquishes it for project.
- iii. **Opportunity Entrepreneur:** They have structural approach to establishing an enterprise, they are versatile in the area of business management, educated and experienced. They apply both technical and managerial know-how in the management of the business. Besides the broad categories identified by scholars, there are some typology that are common in the diversity of small business managers/ owners these common types as identified by Stokes (1995) are as follows:
 1. **Soloist:** A self employed entrepreneur like plumber, physician etc who operated alone in a specific trade or profession.
 2. **Workforce Builder:** He manages the labour and expertise of others like helmsman in building or construction industry.
 3. **Capital Aggregator:** Business owners with substantial capital these are common in banking and insurance business. They are solvent enough to acquire other substantial and attractive business like Dangote groups.
 4. **Speculators:** They do not establish business of their own but they have money meant to buy goods with expedition. That the price of the commodity will increase in a later period they deal in stock of shares, farm products or manufactured goods (hoarders).
 5. **Key Partner:** It is expanded soloist who allows or invites someone as partner in the business ownership, sometime as a financial backer only.
 6. **Groupier:** Those who join haves together to form a business in form of cooperatives. Key preferred working in small group in share ideas decision and strength craftsman working in a workshop like mechanics, tailors, carpenters etc.
 7. **Professional:** Self employed experts like medical doctors, accountant, architects, Solicitors etc.
 8. **Inventors:** Research innovation, creative inventors who engages in creating or producing a given product for sales.
 9. **High-Tech:** Those with technical expertise to use new technology like computer engineers/ technologist.

- 10. Inveterate Initiator:** An expert who takes the challenges of initiating or setting up of business to be sold later in order to start another

V. FUNCTIONS OF ENTREPRENEUR

In trying to identify the functions of entrepreneur Usman (2006) states the following:

- i. It makes one to pursuing opportunity, activities with passion for a purpose, living proactively and leverage resources to create value.
- ii. Exploration and exploitation of business opportunities.
- iii. Sourcing, directing and combining production inputs (resources) as factors or production.
- iv. Involved in range of activities leading to establishment and management of business enterprise making decision, bearing risks and uncertainty to achieve success and pursuance of investment opportunities often associated with creativity and innovation.

VI. RELEVANCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS ACQUISITIONS

Mopelola and Momodu (2012) states that the need of acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among youth at the basic education in Nigeria is significance in our Universities curriculum such that youth are trained to acquire useful skills at their graduation which enables them contribute meaningful in the society. Benjamin and Tughgba (2012) held basically the imperative of having entrepreneurial education is to enable children acquire skills that they will begin to initiate profit making enterprise and that will create jobs so that the teaming unemployed can be absorbed. When such skills are acquired at the basic education levels as the young entrepreneurs grow, the idea will grow with them.

In a related view, Cyril (2010) recognized the high cost of education in the country also calls for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills at the basic education level. This has been necessitated by the fact that education at any level above basic education is going beyond the reach of the poor. These skills acquired at basic education level can enable the basic level graduate to initiate economically viable business ventures that will yield earnings which they can use to support themselves in higher levels of education and as well support their family members (Benjamin and Tughgba 2012). Supporting on ways in curbing youth restiveness in Nigeria, Benjamin and Tughgba (2012) states that the increasing societal vices in Nigeria are another need for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills at the basic education level, this is because when the youth acquired these skills, they can engage in profitable economic ventures and have no time for societal vices like political smuggling, cultism, religious faradism, armed robbery, ethnic and clannish militia, terrorism etc. This will help to rids societies of such evils, this is paramount that at this level the skills can be more easily taught and learnt than when the learners have become corrupted, because at the basic education they can be more guided into useful business ventures.

VII. BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAM TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURIAL

Looking at business education programs at the basic education level and tertiary institution Aliyu (2006) states that at the basic education level referred to programmed that induce helping develop the students desire to want to study business subjects in the future advanced classes. The business subjects offered at this state will help the students in making up his mind to pursuit business related career later in life. Business study at the basic education level will assist in the guidance program of the vocational education. in the future secondary school the thought of the qualified student may be directed towards the senior secondary school business curriculum while the attention of the students who lacks the basic abilities needed in business occupations may be turned to the non business curriculum. Business affects every member of the society because everyone is a consumer and purchases the goods and services provided by business. All students need to develop a clear concept of social and economic truths and understanding and appreciation of the role business play in our daily lives.

National policy on education (2006) furthered stated goals or objectives of vocational education as: diversified the curriculum of vocational education to cater for the differences in talent, opportunities and roles possessed by or open to students after their secondary school course.

Aliyu (2006) opined that skilled worker in business program comprises of carpenters, the painter, the plumber, the electrician, mechanics etc. all of them go into contracts bills of purchases, supplies and some also sell materials. All of them keep simple records in classifying business education at tertiary institution. Aliyu (2006) states that is the education that covers the post secondary section of the National education system which is given in Universities, Polytechnics, and Colleges of technology including such courses as are given by the prescribed tertiary institutions. The objectives to be achieved through higher education as outlined by the new national policy on education (2006) as this: the acquisition development and inculcation of the proper value-orientation for the survival of the individual and society, the development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environments: the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community.

Aliyu (2006) points it cleared that business program referred to the preparation of people to enter into the business world, to participate in productive activities in an attempt to meet up with the nations needs and also to be able to make wise use of financial rewards in order to attain successful living.

In sorting out opportunities in business programmes towards curbing youth restiveness Momoh (2012) identifies that agricultural resources, natural resources information and communication technology, mechanics, carpenters, welders, kitrens, salons etc. also call for the acquisition to entrepreneurial skill at the basic education level so as to rap, harness and utilize the resources and opportunities and convert them into profit-yielding ventures for individuals, the communities, the states and the nation.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Despite of difficulties in our nation yet individuals youth needs to double their effort towards creating good initiatives in order to develop our dear society. This can not be achieved successfully unless parents change skills in our economy on like China, Germany, America etc. who are not relaying much on government to provide means for surviving rather what an individual can afford to the government and the entire nations.

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